

REMOVABLE PROSTHESES

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Abstract: Reconstruction of the dentition extensively damaged through tooth surface loss may require the use of removable prostheses. This can be the most appropriate type of treatment when either the teeth are very severely worn or the patient wishes a simpler and more economical approach than a fixed reconstruction.

Key words: Removable, prostheses, types.

Removable prostheses treat partial/full tooth loss when other options like bridges/implants are not preferred. Removable dentures are the general name given to dentures that can be taken off by the person.

Such dentures are a common alternative treatment for missing teeth. Movable dentures replace missing teeth with support from oral tissues. They are a cheaper treatment option compared to fixed dentures. There are two main types of movable dentures, partial dentures and full dentures.

The dentures, made of resin in a gum-colored plastic, are designed to sit on the palate and hold the artificial teeth in place. The fit of the dentures is very important as it can affect natural functions such as speaking, eating, and chewing.

Types of Removable Prosthesis

The type of removable prosthesis that can be attached and removed by the

1. **Total Prostheses:** Total dentures used for complete tooth loss in adults. Prostheses that are produced by taking support from the lower and upper jawbone tissue. Dentures (total prostheses) offer comfort as they can be attached and removed. They are usually made of plastic, so color changes may be observed over time.

2. **Partial Prostheses:** A prosthesis applied to mouths where a part of natural teeth are found. They are made of either acrylic or one-piece casting. Partial prostheses that are attached to the main teeth, may not be esthetic due to their wire appearance. Therefore, it is not a prosthesis type that is frequently preferred.

3. **Sensitively Connected Prostheses:** A removable prosthesis type used in cases of multiple tooth loss. They take their support from the remaining natural teeth in the mouth. Prostheses that are attached to teeth with the help of small retaining apparatuses hidden in porcelain crowns, without hooks.

4. **Immediate Prosthesis:** Are used in cases where all the main teeth need to be removed. If the patient does not want to remain toothless, they are temporary healing prostheses that are attached immediately after the natural teeth are removed. When the healing is completed and the tissues become incompatible with these prostheses, the permanent prostheses of the patient are started to be made.

5. **Overdenture Prosthesis:** A prosthesis type that is created by providing support on a few natural teeth or roots that exist in the mouth.

What are the Advantages of Removable Prosthesis?

Missing teeth significantly affect both chewing and speech functions. Therefore, missing teeth should be filled as soon as possible.

1. Removable prostheses are one of the most economical ways to complete missing teeth. In addition to restoring the function of the mouth, these prostheses also help to preserve the shape of the face.

2. Another advantage of removable prosthesis is that some types of **removable prosthesis** treatments do not require tooth cutting.

3. **Removable prosthesis** treatment is completed much faster than implant treatment.

Removable prostheses help people regain lost teeth and live their daily lives comfortably. However, when these prostheses are first fitted, some people may experience a period of adjustment. During this period, the person wearing the **removable prosthesis** may have some problems with speech, eating, chewing, and keeping the prosthesis in place. Over time, removable prostheses may wear out or break.

Another disadvantage of removable prostheses is that if the person loses jaw fit, it may be necessary to replace the dental prostheses.

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